

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Toward Inclusive Futures: Indian Picturebooks, Queer Theory, and the Call for Empathetic Worldbuilding

Spandan Ghosh

Research Scholar,
Department of English and MEL,
University of Lucknow,
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh.

Article History: Submitted-17/05/2025, Revised-15/06/2025, Accepted-21/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

This paper examines the intersection of queer theory and Indian picturebooks for children through an analysis of *The Boy in the Cupboard*, *Maya the Warrior*, *Ritu Weds Chandni*, *When I Grow Up*, *Guthli Has Wings* and *The Weightlifting Princess*. Using José Esteban Muñoz's concept of disidentification and Sedgwick's insights into the depathologisation of homosexuality, the paper explores how these picturebooks actively challenge heteronormative structures, redefine gender binaries, and foreground queer narratives. Set against the backdrop of India's evolving legal and cultural landscape following the 2018 decriminalisation of homosexuality, this paper argues that such picturebooks serve as critical tools for social transformation. They challenge exclusionary norms while offering young readers a roadmap for inclusive futures, positioning queer children's literature as a vital site for the generation of counterpublics and collective belonging.

Keywords: Queer Childhoods, Picturebooks in India, Gender Nonconformity, Queer Futurity, Inclusive Narratives.

Queer Theory, Childhood, and the Call for Inclusive Recognition

Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, often regarded as the pioneer of queer theory, explores in her seminal 1991 work *How to Bring Your Kids Up Gay* the cultural rationale and enduring desire for gay erasure, exemplified by the 1980 reclassification of homosexuality and the simultaneous introduction of Gender Identity Disorder of Children in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual* (DSM III). Sedgwick argues that this apparent depathologisation of homosexuality is intricately tied to the reinforcement of masculine gender norms, characterizing the effeminacy of boys as a pathological condition. She interprets this shift as part of a broader effort to conceptualise gender and sexuality as interdependent yet distinct analytical categories (20). Beneath this superficial alteration in societal stigmatisation through medical pathologisation lies a more profound wish for the nonexistence of gay men. Sedgwick asserts that addressing this issue requires not only removing the stigma and pathology associated with effeminate boys and the gay men they often become but also cultivating a desire for “gay people in the immediate world” (26).

Fast forward twenty-five years after Sedgwick’s influential publication, queer children have achieved greater visibility in political, cultural, and social spheres. The effeminate boy, alongside other queer youth, has emerged as a central figure in contemporary queer and transgender theory. Non-binary identities are increasingly embraced by the same institutions that once marginalised them. However, such acceptance remains fragile and subject to changing socio-political landscapes. Nonetheless, there has been a discernible shift toward affirmation and recognition.

This paper explores the convergence of queer theory and Indian picturebooks, focusing on queer theory’s analysis of childhood, especially the identity struggles of queer children. It seeks to stimulate discussion on “queer childhood studies” (Dyer 10), within Indian scholarship through a

comparative analysis of chosen contemporary Indian picturebooks. The research investigates how young people resist heteronormativity in/through picturebooks by occupying queer spaces and how they manage queerness within a heteronormative society. Concurrently, the study assesses picturebooks' function as instruments for promoting cultural resistance in public domains.

Reading Resistance: Queer Childhoods in Indian Picturebooks

The picturebook *The Boy in the Cupboard*, written by Harshala Gupte and illustrated by Priya Dali, shows Karan, whose favourite spot in the world is his cupboard. Whenever he is not at school, it is here where he can be found. He quickly returns to his safe space even if he steps out to play with his friends. Strangely, no one has ever asked him why—until one day, Ma does. Although she usually has all the answers, Ma is surprised by what Karan reveals this time. She asks, “Darling, why don’t you come out and play? I wonder what you do in there all day?” The worried mother inquires whether he is scared inside, and the boy answers, “The cupboard is dark at all times, Ma. No matter the night no matter the day, The cupboard stays the same, Even if I’m away.”

The story centres on Karan, who delights in draping himself in his mother’s sari and adorning his hair with flowers. He faces ridicule from other boys for his pink cricket bat and kitchen play set. Tired of the taunts, he retreats to his cupboard—a poignant metaphor for the closet. Concerned for her son, his mother reassures him of her unconditional support, no matter what.

Judith Butler’s concept of heteronormativity shows varied application across societies, refuting universal definitions. In India, childhood gender socialisation rigidly enforces heteronormativity via strict gender rules, including dress codes, behaviour rules, and limited interactions between genders. This prompts key questions: How are children who resist these norms treated? Since such nonconformity inevitably arises in societies with rigid gender roles, will these children be accepted

or marginalised? Because childhood is a crucial period when challenges to norms often take root (Christopher 700), exploring these through picturebooks that portray children's lives in India becomes essential. Such an approach calls for an expansive, inclusive notion of childhood—one that embraces queer futurity and resists the erasure of queer temporalities within dominant developmental narratives.

In her wordless picturebook *Maya the Warrior*, Priya Dali draws her own experiences of growing up. She paints the girl with short hair unable to fit within her school's environment. She is taunted, ridiculed, and pushed aside by her peers. She remains unaccommodated for her short hair within the girls' group while the boys refuse her for her biological gender. In one of the pages, an illustration shows that she is inquisitive and wonders how riding a bike like a boy might feel. Another illustration shows Maya browsing her family album, where one of the photos shows her mother picking up her husband in her arms.

Representation and Empathy: The Role of Publishers and Creators

In contrast, another photo shows the mother wearing a crown. Maya wishes to become a warrior and is so in her dreams when she falls asleep. "In picturebooks for children, there is a very binary representation of things. How good boys or good girls behave, or what they look like. There is an urgent need to revisit this," says Dali in an interview with *The Print*.

Bengaluru-based publishing house Pratham Books, known for titles like *Friends Under the Summer Sun* and *I Want to Ride a Motorbike*, tackles important themes of gender identity through their publications. They collaborate with authors, illustrators, editors, and subject matter experts to authentically and sensitively address these topics. "It's critical to see diversity in children's books. After all, books are ... real, imagined, familiar, new. And, it's even more important for

children to see themselves reflected in books and at the same time, embrace diversity and inclusion through these stories,” emphasises Bijal Vachharajani, senior editor at Pratham Books in an interview to *Deccan Herald*.

Priya Dali agrees, underscoring the importance of incorporating queer themes in children’s literature to foster empathy and validate lived experiences. Books can help young readers navigate the world while allowing creators to present vivid and imaginative visions of realities that may not yet exist. “Maya and Karan look like they could be the readers’ classmates. They show how in the same world, same school, same classroom, someone who is not you could be living a totally different version of what you go through,” Priya explains (*Deccan*). Introducing queer themes to children not only provides relatable representation but also broadens perspectives. She further emphasises that any picturebook immerses readers in someone else’s journey, offering a glimpse into their world.

Imagining Futures: Picturebooks as Queer Worldbuilding

Early creative works can significantly impact material world-building and societal development. Picturebooks representing LGBTQ+ themes for children introduce the lives individuals, missing from cultural portrayals, into the sphere of societal and cultural recognition. This nurtures a shared identity and self-validation for individuals who feel disconnected from those with comparable gender and sexual identities. Therefore, examining the types of representations and imagined collectives is crucial in exploring the transformative power of literature focused on LGBTQ+ themes for children. Imagined realities influence what is achievable. Beyond world-building, these books function as records of history, illuminating what was considered conceivable and feasible at various historical points. During the late 1990s, Kenneth Kidd compellingly contended that

lesbian and gay-themed novels for young adults are a valuable “index to changing attitudes toward homosexuality” (Miller 29). He observed that analyzing young adult fiction demonstrates a progression from framing homosexuality as a societal problem to portraying homophobia as a social issue (Christopher 700).

Multicultural children’s literature scholars have extensively studied the politics of inclusive children’s picturebooks and their potential social impact. For example, Rudine Sims Bishop, in her influential 1990 essay, “Windows, Mirrors, and Sliding Glass Doors,” famously remarked: “Books are sometimes windows, offering views of worlds that may be real or imagined, familiar or strange. These windows are also sliding glass doors, and readers have only to walk through in imagination to become part of whatever world has been created or recreated by the author. When lighting conditions are just right, however, a window can also be a mirror. Literature transforms human experience and reflects it back to us, and in that reflection we can see our own lives and experiences as part of a larger human experience.”

LGBTQ+ children have long struggled to see their “own lives and experiences as part of a larger human experience” (Bishop). Children have felt rejected and dejected, unable to connect with the world-at-large. In India, childhood gender socialisation rigidly enforces heteronormativity via strict gender rules, including dress codes, behaviour rules, and limited interactions between genders. They may face conversion therapy, both overt and subtle, aimed at “correcting” their identities. This includes coercion, medication, psychological counseling, and pressure to conform to normative gender expressions. The tragic outcomes of young individuals subjected to such treatment highlights its dangers and the urgent need for awareness and legal protection. The compounding effects of societal rejection, secrecy, and policing of behavior leads to significant mental health burdens for queer children, such as low self-esteem, hyper-vigilance, and

internalized shame (*Al Jazeera*). This prompts key questions: How are children who resist these norms treated? Since such nonconformity inevitably arises in societies with rigid gender roles, will these children be accepted or marginalised?

The 2018 Supreme Court judgment decriminalising homosexuality in India marks a pivotal turn in engendering inclusivity within children's literature publishers. This landmark decision encouraged publishers to embrace diverse narratives, led libraries to stock these books and inspired readers to buy them. Authors with unique stories suddenly found a space to share their voices. For years, niche publishers such as Gaysi Family and Duckbill Books have been at the forefront of championing this genre. However, major publishing houses, including Penguin Random House India and Scholastic India, have also started welcoming new voices more actively (*Print*). Additionally, bookstores like Kitab Khana in Mumbai, Eureka Bookstore in New Delhi, and Champaka Bookstore in Bengaluru increasingly feature these titles on their shelves. Retailers such as Kitab Khana in Mumbai, Eureka Bookstore in New Delhi, and Champaka Bookstore in Bengaluru now carry these books (*Print*).

Pratham Books' *When I Grow Up* tells the story of a young girl with ambitions in engineering and science to improve her village environment. As Judith Halberstam observes, heteronormativity presumes heterosexual partnerships within the traditional gender distinctions but also enforces conventional expectations regarding the behaviours associated with gender binaries. By presenting a girl challenging these expectations and pursuing goals commonly linked to masculinity, the picturebook encourages children to question entrenched societal expectations about gender and broadens the possibilities girls can envision for themselves. There is also an urgent call to address gender imbalances and the stereotypes assigned in a manly world.

Similarly, the picturebook *The Weightlifting Princess*, reimagines femininity by subverting the conventional portrayal of princesses. This alternative narrative follows Princess Nila, a determined girl who trains to compete in a contest of weightlifting called Surya Championship. Nila embodies strength, determination, and independence, breaking away from the passive, domesticated princess archetype commonly depicted in children's literature. Her robust, muscular physique and tanned skin, described as "golden brown, the colour of sunset", contrast sharply with stereotypical images of princesses characterised by slim bodies, delicate features, and ornate gowns. By redefining beauty and femininity, the picturebook disrupts traditional gender binaries.

This presence and prominence of binaries finds its early resonance with the psychoanalytic theories of Sigmund Freud, whose work simultaneously acknowledged and pathologised deviations from normative gender and sexual roles. Freud remarked that homosexuality was "nothing to be ashamed of, no vice, no degradation; it cannot be classified as an illness, but a variation of sexual function" ("A Letter from Freud"). However, he also described homosexuality as a narcissistic form of object-choice, where individuals sought themselves in their love objects, a process he linked to disturbed libidinal development (On Narcissism 9). Freud's theories often framed homosexuality as an aberration, resulting from an arrested progression through the stages of sexual development. Freud's ambivalence towards deviations from heterosexual norms also finds a counterpoint in the American psychoanalytic approach, which reached a critical juncture in 1952 when the American Psychiatric Association (APA) classified homosexuality as a mental disorder in the *DSM*.

The picturebooks *Ritu Weds Chandni* and *Guthli Has Wings* embody the transformative politics of disidentification as theorised by José Esteban Muñoz. These narratives actively subvert heteronormative norms by creating spaces that nurture resistance and reimagine identity. Muñoz's

concept of “counterpublics” (148) offers a lens to understand how these stories construct alternative cultural frameworks through acts of “worldmaking” (195). Both picturebooks use disidentification as a tool to challenge gender roles and heteronormativity while simultaneously envisioning new possibilities for selfhood and community (Christopher 701).

Ritu Weds Chandni portrays the love between two women partners marrying through customary rituals. While many close to them joyfully join in the celebrations, a few relatives, disapproving of the unconventional union, attempt to disrupt the wedding procession by throwing water. Ayesha chooses to intervene. She starts to dance as an act of defiance and resistance, and the scene is immediately transformed. This act is what Muñoz describes as “innovative resistance” that reclaims public space and redefines cultural norms. Through her intervention, Ayesha demonstrates how “counterpublics” can emerge even within traditionally rigid social settings.

Similarly, in *Guthli Has Wings*, Guthli in her assertion against her family’s attempts to misgender her represents an act of disidentification. She is a child who finds happiness wearing her sister’s clothes but faces resistance from her family, who insist she wears “boys” clothing. Guthli confronts this misgendering directly, asking her mother, “I want to be a fairy! Why do you keep saying I’m a boy when I’m a girl?” Her family’s inability to accept her identity damages her emotional well-being, driving her to withdraw from them and find solace among trees and chickens—companions who accept her without judgment. Eventually, Guthli’s mother empathises with her suffering and brings her a frock, telling her to “wear it and be what you want.” Muñoz’s framework explains how Guthli’s withdrawal to the company of trees and chickens can be viewed as her rejecting imposed gender norms and creating an alternative space for self-expression. Guthli’s mother’s eventual acceptance, symbolised by the gift of a frock, becomes a moment of “worldmaking,” where Guthli’s identity is validated and celebrated. Whatever has been domesticated through

stereotyping is questioned through the child's expression. There is resistance to heteronormative constraints, and the counterpublics become little pockets of action and acceptance.

Queer theory today underscores the urgency of social change, viewing the present as a pivotal moment for action. By equipping us with tools to critique regimes of gender and sexual normativity, it not only identifies systemic issues but also offers the imaginative space to envision alternatives. When combined with diverse methodologies, from ethnography to archival research, queer theory emerges as both an essential and creative tool for interpretation. More than an academic framework, it calls for immediate and practical worldmaking that challenges normalisation and centres queer lives. The present becomes a dynamic arena, a “playground” for queer theorists to reimagine and reshape the world. The stakes are undeniably high, and the lives enriched by these transformative efforts demand nothing less than committed action.

Works Cited:

Bishop, Rudine Sims. “Windows, Mirrors, and Sliding Glass Doors.” *Perspectives: Choosing and Using Books for the Classroom*, vol. 6, no. 3, 1990. Science Regional Library, <https://scenicregional.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Mirrors-Windows-and-Sliding-Glass-Doors.pdf>.

Christopher, Ashitha Mary. ““The Boy in the Cupboard”: Children in Indian Comics and their Subversion of Heteronormative Interpellation.” *Journal of Graphic Novels and Comics*, vol. 15, no. 5, 2024, pp. 699-715. *Taylor and Francis Online*, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21504857.2024.2313049>.

Dali, Priya. *Maya the Warrior*. Pratham Books, 2020.

Dyer, Hannah. *The Queer Aesthetics of Childhood: Asymmetries of Innocence and the Cultural Politics of Child Development*. Rutgers U P, 2020.

“Queer futurity and childhood innocence: Beyond the injury of development. Global Studies of Childhood.” *Global Studies of Childhood*, vol. 7, no. 3, Sept. 2017, pp. 290-302. Sage, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2043610616671056>

Freud, Sigmund. “Historical Notes: A Letter from Freud.” *American Journal of Psychiatry*, vol. 107, no. 10, Apr. 1951, pp. 786–787. *American Psychiatric Publishing*, doi:10.1176/ajp.107.10.786.

Freud, Sigmund. *On Narcissism: An Introduction*. Read Books Ltd., 2013.

Gogoi, Priyadarshini. *When I Grow Up*. Pratham Books, 2020.

Gupte, Harshala. *The Boy in the Cupboard*. Illustrated by Priya Dali, Gaysi Media Pvt. Limited and Lettori, LLP, 2021.

Halberstam, Jack. *Female Masculinity*. Duke UP, 1998.

Joseph, Krupa. “Queer Themes in Indian Books for Children.” *Deccan Herald*, 17 Aug. 2021, <https://www.deccanherald.com/india/karnataka/bengaluru/queer-themes-in-indian-books-for-children-969645.html>.

Miller, Jennifer. *The Transformative Potential of LGBTQ+ Children’s Picturebooks*. UP of Mississippi, 2022, pp. 29+

Muñoz, José Esteban. *Disidentifications: Queers of Colour and the Performance of Politics*. U of Minnesota P, 1999.

Narang, Gaurvi. “Indian LGBTQ+ Fiction is Out of the ‘Cupboard’. With a Non-elitist, Non-Western Language.” *The Print*, 9 July 2023, <https://theprint.in/ground-reports/indian-lgbtq-fiction-is-out-of-the-cupboard-with-a-non-elitist-non-western-language/1661403/>.

Narvankar, Ameya. *Ritu Weds Chandni*. Yali Publishing LLC, 2020.

Payal Dhar. "I Have Sacrificed a Lot": Growing up LGBTQ+ in India." *Al Jazeera*. 21 June 2021, <https://www.aljazeera.com/features/2021/6/21/i-have-sacrificed-a-lot-growing-up-lgbtq-in-india>.

Parthasarathy, Aarthi. *I Want to Ride a Motorbike*. Illustrated by Rai, Pratham Books, 2020.

Pathak, Ashutosh. *Friends Under the Summer Sun*. Illustrated by Kanak Shashi, Pratham Books, 2020.

Rejendra, Sowmya. *The Weightlifting Princess*. Illustrated by Debasmita Dasgupta, Pratham Books, 2018.

Shashi, Kanak. *Guthli Has Wings*. Tulika Publishers, 2019.

Sedgwick, Eve Kosofsky. "How to Bring Your Kids up Gay." *Social Text*, no. 29, 1991, pp. 18–27. *JSTOR*, <https://doi.org/10.2307/466296>.